

Australian Research Data Commons

Analysis of HTC Demand and Deployment Models

Final Report

GFA-177: Analysis of HTC Demand and Deployment Models

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Analysis of HTC demand and deployment models
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1. Executive summary

This discovery activity has identified a need for HTC services to support national computing workloads. The use cases examined, from NCRIS funded Virtual Laboratories, are already using HTC services and they expect their needs to increase. They have currently implemented their own private HTC services. These are using approximately 539 vCPUs across the country from the Nectar Research Cloud, plus at least 340 cores from MASSIVE's M3 and QCIF's Awoonga HTC service.

These observations have been made:

- A national HTC service is attractive. For Virtual Laboratories implementing their own private HTC service, it can reduce their duplication of effort. For infrastructure providers, it allows them to avoid having to reject users because the system is full, and allows them to benefit from improving utilisation versus cost.
- But for the benefit to be fully achieved, requires the available resources to be balanced with demand. Too much resources and idle resources are no longer cost effective. Too little resources and performance is impacted, discouraging users and making it unsuitable for tasks that require better performance.
- Therefore, HTC services needs to grow with growing demand; otherwise the benefits are no longer fully achieved because the resources versus demand has become unbalanced.
- Not all tasks are suitable for HTC, but those that are could be moved off other infrastructure; freeing them up for workloads they have been optimised for.

A series of steps have been recommended to support the growing demand for HTC services to run national workloads. The first step is to enable the Virtual Laboratories to work together, to design a HTC service based on the HTCondor software. Implement that service using Nectar Research Cloud virtual machines and dedicated hardware, and then growing the compute capability in balance with growing demand.

The important first step is to encourage the Virtual Laboratories to collaborate: to share expertise, reduce duplicated effort and to find natural synergies.

2. Introduction

2.1. Background

The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) has identified one of its strategic themes as “Storage and Compute”, the providing of foundation infrastructure.

In 2019, the ARDC conducted a number of discovery activities, in order to identify where investment can be most effectively targeted. The *Analysis of HTC Demand and Deployment Models* is one of those discovery activities, and was conducted by the Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation (QCIF).

2.2. Purpose

This report documents the discovery activity to identify the demand for High Throughput Computing (HTC) services in the Australian research community, and to identify issues and needs.

2.3. Scope

The project focuses on the needs of the Australian research community at a national level. It focuses on needs that are outside the scope of any single university or research organisation to provide, since they are not only used by staff from that organisation.

2.4. Glossary

ARDC	Australia Research Data Commons
CVL	Characterisation Virtual Laboratory
HPC	High Performance Computing
HTC	High Throughput Computing
QCIF	Queensland Cyber Infrastructure Foundation

2.5. Overview

Chapter 3 describes the project, approach and defines High Throughput Computing.

Chapter 4 contains the findings from the project.

Chapter 5 identifies emergent themes.

Chapter 6 identifies issues that were discovered.

Chapter 7 concludes with a summary and recommendations.

Appendix A contains the details about the case studies.

Appendix B contains the references.

3. Project overview

3.1. Project goals

This project aims to identify the demand for High Throughput Computing (HTC) tools and services, and to identify issues and needs.

3.2. High Throughput Computing

Modern research methods, in many fields, involves processing data and performing computations that require a large amount of computing resources. This project specifically focuses on a type of computing called High Throughput Computing (HTC).

3.2.1. Definition

High Throughput Computing (HTC) is defined by the European Grid Infrastructure as:

A computing paradigm that focuses on the efficient execution of a large number of loosely-coupled tasks. Given the minimal parallel communication requirements, the tasks can be executed on clusters or physically distributed resources... HTC systems are typically optimised to maximise the throughput over a long period of time and a typical metric is jobs per month or year. [EGI2012]

For the purposes of this project, the key features of HTC are:

- the use of a large number of multiple computers;
- those computers are loosely connected; and
- they are operated with the overall goal of maximising the throughput over a long period of time.

HTC is implemented as a scheduled environment, where the demand for resources is time shifted to improve the average utilisation of the computing infrastructure. Users submit jobs for processing, and a scheduler runs them when resources are available. Utilisation can be improved, but at the expense of latency, because jobs may have to wait for other jobs to finish before they can run.

Some tasks are not efficiently resourced by HTC services. Tasks that require an immediate or guaranteed response time would require either dedicated resources and/or a significant investment in scheduling logic to meet the typical demands of those tasks. Such an investment in resources (infrastructure or capability development) would reduce the overall efficiency of a HTC service, but may be acceptable if there are other secondary efficiencies. Also, some tasks do not have an end condition. For example, a Web server is running a continuous loop (that waits for requests and processes them) with an expected lifetime well in excess of normal limits for scheduled environments. Attempting to shoehorn this kind of workload into a scheduled environment carries a cost that makes such an endeavor unpalatable.

While tasks suitable for HTC services can often be run on non-HTC services, the opposite is usually not true. But running HTC-suitable tasks on non-HTC services carries an opportunity cost, due to the extra investment those platforms require to meet the non-HTC demands being

wasted on the HTC workload. Therefore, if suitable HTC services were available, it would be more cost effective to run them on the HTC services.

3.2.2. Distinction from HPC

This project treats High Performance Computing (HPC) as distinct from HTC.

HPC aims to combine the capabilities of multiple servers together to solve a single task, while a HTC task is made up of one or more independent subtasks that fit on the resources of a single server. Though this distinction becomes less clear when storage subsystems (particularly of the clustered variety) are also considered. In this case, the distinguishing feature becomes sensitivity to latency; performance of HPC workloads are strongly dependent on interconnect latency and features such as Remote Direct Memory Access (RDMA) transport, while HTC workloads are less impacted.

A strict numerical definition of the difference between HTC and HPC would require an Amdahl's law based analysis that is beyond the scope of this document.

There are some applications which require HPC, and will never run successfully on HTC. Such applications are designed to require supercomputing interconnects, and will not function without them.

3.3. Approach

In this project, interviews were conducted with Virtual Laboratories to determine their current and future demand for HTC services, and to identify any special needs they may have.

Virtual Laboratories funded by the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) were chosen for the case studies. Although individual universities and organisations are both operators of HTC services and significant users of them, that usage is typically restricted to one institution. Whereas, this project is focused on demand for national computing infrastructure. Therefore, the NCRIS funded Virtual Laboratories is a good representative of current usage that serves end users from multiple universities and organisations. Obviously, there will be demand from other groups: the aim is not to exhaustively identify all possible demand, but to treat the Virtual Laboratories as a representation of demand.

These Virtual Laboratories were used as case studies:

- Biodiversity and Climate Change Virtual Laboratory (BCCVL);
- Characterisation Virtual Laboratory (CVL) in Queensland;
- Characterisation Virtual Laboratory (CVL) on MASSIVE;
- Galaxy Australia;
- ecocloud; and
- Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN).

An additional interview was conducted with The University of Queensland's Research Computing Centre (UQ RCC), about their experiences with running HTC jobs on commercial cloud services. This was used to inform the issues section of this report.

4. Findings

4.1. Summary of case studies

All the case studies were found to be using HTC, and they expect to require more resources in the future (as demand for their services grow, and they introduce new capabilities). A brief summary of their current HTC usage is:

- Biodiversity and Climate Change Virtual Laboratory (BCCVL) runs a HTC on 40 Nectar Research Cloud virtual machines, using approximately 116 vCPUs in total.
- Characterisation Virtual Laboratory in Queensland (CVL@QLD) runs a HTC on 4 virtual machines on QCIF's Awoonga HTC cluster, using 80 cores. Each has one GPU. CVL processes large datasets, so it has implementations around the country, located near the instruments producing and storing the data. The CVL@QLD is the part located in Queensland, with fast network connections to QCIF's QRISdata collection storage service.
- Characterisation Virtual Laboratory on MASSIVE (CVL@MASSIVE) runs on the MASSIVE HPC/HTC, with approximately 5% of the 5200 cores dedicated for national CVL users (i.e. non-partners) and all of the cores are available for MASSIVE partners.
- Galaxy Australia runs a HTC using 277 vCPUs in the Nectar Research Cloud, in Queensland, Melbourne and Canberra.
- ecocloud runs a HTC using 116 vCPUs in the Nectar Research Cloud.
- Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN) has a number of activities. Those which are relevant to HTC were:
 - Threatened Species Index (TSX) which runs once a year, using 25,000 jobs running on approximately 100 cores for 10 hours.
 - OzFlux currently runs on individual researcher's laptops, but is a candidate for running on HTC.
 - Collaborative Environment for Scholarly Research and Analysis (CoESRA) Virtual Desktop uses a HTC cluster running on 30 vCPUs in the Nectar Research Cloud.
 - Remote sensing data processing currently runs on individual researcher's computers, but is a candidate for running on HTC.

In summary, the case studies are using approximately 539 vCPUs from the Nectar Research Cloud, plus at least 340 cores from MASSIVE's M3 and QCIF's Awoonga HTC service. This does not include the temporary virtual machines used for the TERN Threatened Species Index, since they are only used for a short period of time each year.

Relevant points from the case studies are highlighted in the subsequent sections of this chapter. The full details of the case studies can be found in Appendix A.

4.2. Current demand for HTC

4.2.1. HTC for non-interactive jobs

High Throughput Computing (HTC) is currently being used by all of the case studies. For example, BCCVL, TERN and Galaxy Australia are examples of using HTC for running non-interactive batch jobs.

- BCCVL uses HTC to run compute-intensive jobs submitted by researchers. The researchers creates jobs from a selection of R scripts. HTC allows end users to perform compute-intensive processing, and BCCVL provides them access to large-scale computing without the end user needing to understand the details of HTC.
- The TERN Threatened Species Index uses HTC to perform compute-intensive processing when the index needs to be regenerated with new data. HTC gives TERN access to a large amount of compute over a short period of time, whereas dedicated resources would be idle most of the time, since the index is only regenerated once a year.
- Galaxy Australia uses HTC to run genomic and bioinformatic jobs for end users. Those jobs run programs from a curated set of over 500 available programs. Galaxy Australia processes about 50,000 jobs per month.

4.2.2. HTC for interactive jobs

Some of the other case studies use HTC for running interactive jobs. For example, CVL@QLD, CVL@MASSIVE, TERN CoESRA and ecocloud.

- CVL@QLD, CVL@MASSIVE and TERN CoESRA uses HTC to run virtual desktop environments. A job is submitted to the HTC system when a user starts a session. A virtual desktop is started when the job runs. The job continues to run until the user terminates the session, or is terminated by the HTC service. The user remotely connects to the virtual desktop using a remote desktop client (either a standalone VNC program or a Web-based implementation).
- ecocloud uses a similar approach for running Jupyter Notebooks and R Studio, instead of virtual desktops.

4.2.3. HTC infrastructure used

In the absence of a national HTC service, the case studies used HPC services provided by organisations that support national research (such as QCIF and MASSIVE), or (more commonly) have implemented their own HTC service on a set of virtual machines in the Nectar Research Cloud.

- Galaxy Australia, BCCVL, ecocloud and TERN CoESRA used HTC services they have implemented on top of a pool of virtual machines in the Nectar Research Cloud.
- CVL@QLD and TERN Threatened Species Index used HTC services provided by QCIF and The University of Queensland. Namely, Awoonga and Tinaroo.
- CVL@MASSIVE is using the service provided by MASSIVE's M3.

CVL@QLD is implementing a mixed approach to obtain compute resources. Workloads submitted by end users from The University of Queensland will be sent to that institution's Wiener cluster, while other workloads will continue to be processed on the Awoonga HTC.

4.3. Future demand for HTC

The case studies have all indicated they will have an increasing demand for HTC services. This is to support growing demand on the Virtual Laboratories, as well as to support additional capabilities the Virtual Laboratories wish to provide. In particular:

- CVL@QLD is already limited by the availability of GPUs in the HTC it is currently using, and it needs to support a growing number of end users.
- CVL@MASSIVE expects new uses for HTC to arise from end users introduced to MASSIVE through their use of the CVL@MASSIVE Virtual Laboratory.
- ecocloud intends to implement a new feature to allow researchers to perform compute-intensive operations (similar to what BCCVL currently offers).
- TERN Threatened Species Index would like to use a nationally available HTC service. Once a year, it needs to perform a significant amount of computation in a short period of time. This processing task is highly suitable for HTC, since it can be parallelised into many separate and independent jobs.
- TERN remote sensing data processing has similar data processing needs, where computationally-intensive batch processing needs to be performed on an irregular basis.
- TERN OzFlux will also benefit from moving to HTC. It irregularly performs batch processing on separate datasets. Moving to HTC will reduce the need to run it on the researcher's individual laptops—reducing the administrative overheads for the researchers and improve the reproducibility of the process by having a centrally managed processing pipeline.

It is reasonable to expect other Virtual Laboratories and software services will also have a demand for HTC services, since all of the case studies have chosen that type of solution.

4.4. Software platforms for HTC

The case studies used traditional job schedulers in their HTC services, such as: SLURM, Celery and PBS Professional®.

While traditional job schedulers can be used to implement a HTC system, some schedulers have been specifically designed to implement HTC systems. The two most prominent ones are HTCondor and BOINC.

These both offer a “cycle scavenging” feature, where compute resources can offer themselves to the HTC infrastructure when they have spare capacity. Individuals and organisations agree to contribute their spare compute resources to the HTC system. For example, in the case of an individual, they can install an agent on their desktop computer that offers it to the pool when its keyboard and mouse has not been used and the computer would otherwise hibernate. When the computer is required by its owner, HTC jobs running on it are halted—the computer's owner has priority over the HTC jobs. Checkpoints can be used to save partially calculated results, so they are not lost when jobs are halted.

HTCondor

HTCondor is developed by the University of Wisconsin-Madison. The field of High Throughput Computing (HTC) was developed by HTCondor (originally called “Condor”) and it has been refined and evolved over the years [UWM2019].

HTCondor uses an attribute based mechanism for scheduling jobs. In a single *pool*, *resources* advertise their availability and *agents* advertise their needs; then a *matchmaker* finds resources with suitable attributes to meet the agent’s needed attributes, and introduces them to each other. Through *flocking*, multiple pools can be connected together to share and use each other’s resources—controlled by policies implemented in the matchmakers. The attributes describing the capabilities of a resource is represented by a schema-less data structure (i.e. it is highly extensible); and the requirements of an agent are defined by *expressions* that are evaluated on the resource capabilities.

HTCondor supports different types of running environments (which it calls “universes”), including Docker and Singularity containers. A snapshot of a running job can be saved as a *checkpoint*, so it can be restarted from that point. Jobs can also be *migrated* between resources.

HTCondor is widely used: in April 2004 there were at least 999 pools and 37966 hosts [THAI2004]. It has been used with commercial Cloud services, such as Google Cloud [BHAT2017] and Azure [SRIR2017].

BOINC

Berkeley Open Infrastructure for Network Computing (BOINC) was developed to provide volunteer computing in the SETI@HOME project [BERK2019]. It can also be used with dedicated compute nodes—as demonstrated by the University of Texas, who extended BOINC to run jobs on Cloud virtual machines and to support Docker packages [SING2019][AROR2019]. Currently, BOINC is popular for volunteer computing projects that perform a specific task, rather than as a means to provide generic HTC services.

4.5. Examples of national/international HTC services

Two examples of national/international HTC services are:

- Open Science Grid, which supports opportunistic usage and resource sharing for research in the United States. The OSG itself does not own any compute resources. Instead, it links together compute resources contributed from over 100 sites across the US. Each site runs their own HTC system (e.g. HTCondor, LFS, PBS and TORQUE, SGE or SLURM) and contribute idle resources to the Open Science Grid [OSG2019].
- The European Grid infrastructure is a federation of cloud providers and data centres across Europe and worldwide [EGI2019].

These services require the agreement and cooperation of the computer’s owner, and is therefore difficult to achieve. Individuals and organisations voluntarily contribute their computing services if they expect to have spare capacity they will not be using themselves.

5. Emergent themes

5.1. HTC demand

There is a current demand for HTC services, and this demand is growing. The virtual laboratories examined are using at least 539 vCPUs and 340 cores for HTC, and they expect their needs to grow in the future—to be able to support an increasing workload from their end users and to implement new capabilities. Most of the use case have implemented their HTC services using virtual machines on the Nectar Research Cloud.

Note: the actual size of the current demand will be larger than this, since this is not an exhaustive study. There will be contributions from other Virtual Laboratories and projects which were not examined in this discovery activity.

Most of these HTC services are operated by the Virtual Laboratory for their own use. This gives them total control over the service, and the ability to better predict how the HTC service will perform (since it will only run jobs from that one Virtual Laboratory). But there is a duplication of effort, in building and maintaining these private HTC services.

From an architectural point of view, there is no load sharing between the different Virtual Laboratories. If one Virtual Laboratory has idle resources, it can't be used by other Virtual Laboratories. If one Virtual Laboratory has increased demand, it can't use any resources outside of its own pool. Throughput maybe maximised for the resources within one private HTC service, but not across all the HTC services.

These Virtual Laboratories all have a need to increase the amount of computing capacity available to it. For those using the Nectar Research Cloud, they will be looking at obtaining a larger allocation of Nectar resources—placing an increased demand on Nectar resources.

5.2. Providing HTC

Computing service providers have an ongoing challenge to satisfy an increasing demand for computing capability in a cost effective manner. HTC offers a way of doing that.

There is no fixed upper bound to the number of users a HTC system can support. Therefore, the service provider is not faced with the problem of the service being fully allocated, when a new user wishes to use the service. But the latency on users' jobs increases as the workload increases. Finding the right balance is a challenge.

There is a balance between capacity and performance. For the HTC service provider, having a HTC service with less capacity than demand is more cost efficient: if there are more jobs than resources to run them, idle resources are kept to a minimum. On the other hand, a HTC service with more capacity than demand performs better: if there are more resources than jobs, they can be scheduled to run with less latency, but idle resources is a wasted expense. For the HTC service user, if the latency and performance becomes unacceptable, they will have to use (possibly more expensive) alternatives.

Although the current demand does not justify dedicated hardware for a national HTC service, growing demand may eventually change that. At that point, it becomes more cost effective to provide dedicated hardware to support a national HTC service. Hardware for HTC can be

cheaper than for Cloud computing, since the level of storage redundancy required is less. Hardware for HTC can be cheaper than for HPC, since it does not require that high level of network interconnections.

5.3. Cloud and HPC

It is important to recognise that Cloud computing and High Performance Computing will always play an important part of the national infrastructure. HTC does not—and cannot—replace them. Some tasks require the special capabilities Cloud and HPC have been optimised for.

However, the addition of a national HTC service could take some of the load off the Nectar Research Cloud and peak HPC facilities. Tasks suitable for HTC don't have to run on them, freeing up resources for tasks that do need the type of computing they are optimised for.

6. Issues

In examining these use cases, several important issues about HTC were identified. A HTC service will need to consider and address these issues.

6.1. Data storage and transfer

Data handling is critical to the success of HTC. Data needs to be transferred to and from the machines running the jobs—which consumes time and consumes bandwidth—as well as temporary and final results need to be stored. The design choices made in this area will affect the performance of the system and the financial cost of using it.

Data storage and transfer is especially important when very large datasets are involved. For example, this is a significant issue for CVL@QLD and CVL@MASSIVE, which uses very large datasets that sometimes need to be processed quickly. The CVL@QLD has addressed this issue by deliberately using a HTC service that is geographically close to the storage where the datasets are stored, and has high-speed links between them. Since high-speed links over longer distances are more expensive and less practical, instruments at other locations will need to use local compute resources—which is why CVL operates in different locations around the country.

The ingress and egress costs can both be significant, both technically and financially. Affecting the performance of the job, data transfer consumes time and bandwidth. If HTC workloads are run on commercial Cloud providers, being conscious of the volume-based and/or operation-based charges will be important.

The UQ RCC use case found that data egress charges represented a large part of the overall financial cost of using commercial cloud services. By optimising its jobs, that particular use case was able to avoid significant data ingress charges.

It is possible to use compression techniques to reduce the size of the data, but there is a trade-off between the size reduction and the compute time required. Compressing data more requires more compute time to perform, so there is a point where the costs outweigh the benefits. In the UQ RCC use case, effort was expended to find an optimal trade-off between processing time and data size. The workload was originally designed for an on-premise HTC cluster, and was made up of 500,000 jobs that executed a program for 2 minutes to perform the calculation and then spent 8 minutes compressing the output data. For the commercial compute platform that was built for this use case, running this workload as initially designed would have cost \$8,000 in actual calculations and \$32,000 in compression (for a total compute cost of \$40,000). Reducing the level of compression so that it took 2 minutes to compress the data reduced the total compute cost to approximately \$16,000—however, this increased the data footprint by 30TB. Depending on what is done with this data, the extra 30TB represents either: an extra \$3000 in public egress charges if sent to a remote site (not including costs at the remote site), approximately \$9000 per year if left in Amazon S3, or approximately \$700 per year if left in Amazon Glacier Deep Archive.

There can also a trade-off between available bandwidth and compute costs. Commercial cloud providers offer different levels of bandwidth with different levels of compute: low priced compute does not come with high bandwidth, so more expensive compute is required if higher

bandwidth is needed. It can be a complicated calculation to determine the optimal cost, bandwidth and compute to use.

Unless significant assistance, monitoring and control of end users is provided, the unrestricted use of commercial cloud services is a financially risky option for a HTC service. For example, a single job running on a single-core CPU can easily generate in excess of AU\$100,000 in network traffic charges in 48 hours.

Monitoring tools do not solve this problem, since there is a significant delay between when the charges are incurred and when they appear in the cost monitoring tools. In the UQ RCC case study, the AWS usage reporting tools took up to 48 hours to fully report all usage charges. This delay is in addition to any support staff delays that exist, if there is not a 24x7 operations team monitoring usage.

It is important to recognise that on-demand cloud (i.e. spot markets) does not affect data transfer or storage charges. In fact, data storage charges are likely to increase: since data will need to be stored in the Cloud, waiting for affordable cycles to become available; and intermediate results need to be stored in the Cloud, when jobs are paused because affordable cycles are no longer available.

Therefore, data considerations support the use of in-house resources as the more cost-effective and/or less financially risky option.

Caching of frequently used data sets can help reduce the costs and delays of transferring the data. But this introduces a managing overhead, as well as increases the costs of storing data. Optimising how data is cached for particular jobs can also require significant effort.

In summary, finding the right trade-off is important to performance and cost. Ensuring the design assumptions remain true, for the actual jobs that are run, is also important.

6.2. Identity management

A unique POSIX identity is required to run the jobs in HTC services.

Most of the use cases use a single POSIX account, as a shared account for running all the jobs, and manage their own end users. This means the HTC service has no visibility of who the actual end user is, so must rely/trust the Virtual Laboratory to manage what end users can and cannot do. It also means there can be security implications if a job needs to authenticate itself as the end user: for example, to access the end user's private storage systems.

To be able to better support the sharing of HTC resources, ideally a common POSIX identity is needed for end users. Institutional identities cannot be used in this context, since those identities are not nationally unique.

The Australian Access Federation (AAF) currently does not support POSIX identities, so therefore cannot be used for this purpose.

However, it is possible to implement a system to assign POSIX identities to users, building on top of the AAF authentication mechanism. The system would maintain a mapping between AAF logins and a unique POSIX identifier, assigned to the AAF login when the end user registers for a POSIX identifier. QCIF has implemented such a system, and it is being used by CVL@QLD.

6.3. Specialised hardware

Some of the Virtual Laboratories have specific hardware requirements to run their jobs. This limits the HTC services they can use.

In particular:

- CVL@QLD, CVL@MASSIVE and Galaxy Australia needs GPU hardware;
- Galaxy Australia, ecocloud and CVL@QLD have jobs that needed extra memory; and
- BCCVL is investigating the need for a sensitive data environment for processing biosecurity workloads.

7. Conclusion

This discovery activity has identified a need to use HTC services to run national computing workloads. The use cases examined, from NCRIS funded Virtual Laboratories, are already using HTC services and they expect their needs to increase. They have currently implemented their own private HTC services. These are using approximately 539 vCPUs across the country from the Nectar Research Cloud, plus at least 340 cores from MASSIVE's M3 and QCIF's Awoonga HTC service.

These observations have been made:

- A national HTC service is attractive. For Virtual Laboratories implementing their own private HTC service, it can reduce their duplication of effort. For infrastructure providers, it allows them to avoid having to reject users because the system is full, and to benefit from improving utilisation versus cost.
- But for the benefit to be fully achieved, requires the available resources to be balanced with demand. Too much resources and idle resources are no longer cost effective. Too little resources and performance is impacted, discouraging users and making it unsuitable for tasks that require better performance.
- Therefore, HTC services needs to grow with demand; otherwise the benefits are not fully achieved because the resources versus demand has become unbalanced.
- Not all tasks are suitable for HTC, but those that are could be moved off other infrastructure; freeing them up for workloads they have been optimised for.

To meet future demand, a long term vision is required; and incremental steps taken to reach it. To that end, the following recommendations are made for discussion:

1. Enable the Virtual Laboratories to work together to design a HTC service based on the HTCondor software.
2. Implement that HTC service on a dedicated set of Nectar virtual machines.
3. Develop a framework for other organisations to volunteer their spare computing capacities to the HTC service. This could be considered as an in-kind contribution from the organisation.
4. Require new Virtual Laboratories that performs HTC suitable tasks, and encourage existing Virtual Laboratories that need increased capacity, to use the HTC service.
5. As demand grows, more Nectar virtual machines can be added to the HTC service. Since the resources are shared, less resources would be needed than if the Virtual Laboratories individually continued to each run their own private HTC services on the Nectar Research Cloud. Due to the risk of cost blow-out with data transfer costs, commercial cloud is not a practical option for handling growing demand (unless very tight controls are put in place over which jobs can be run on them).
6. When the demand justifies dedicated hardware, move it to dedicated hardware. This will free up compute nodes on the Nectar Research Cloud for other uses.
7. As demand continues to grow, plan to meet it by contributing virtual machines from the Nectar Research Cloud, until more dedicated hardware is justified.

The first step encourages the Virtual Laboratories to share their expertise and collaborate around the use of HTC. Collaboration has both short term and long term benefits—not just in HTC, but in other areas where the Virtual Laboratories have shared requirements.

8. Acknowledgements

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Appendix A: Case studies

This appendix describes the case studies that were examined in the project. It describes their aims, current and future computation needs.

A.1. BCCVL

A.1.1. Introduction

The Biodiversity and Climate Change Virtual Laboratory (BCCVL) allows users to select pre-canned models to run. When the results are ready, the users receive an email notification.

Users of BCCVL have access to the benefits of using HTC without needing to understand HTC systems. They also do not have to be concerned with installing and maintaining their own software, which can be difficult when there are dependencies on specific package versions and dependencies between packages.

A.1.2. Current implementation

BCCVL currently runs its own compute cluster of Nectar virtual machines comprising of 40 virtual machines, each with either two or four vCPUs (approximately 116 vCPUs in total). They are all in the NCI availability zone for performance reasons, since NCI virtual machines are backed by solid-state drives (SSD).

Scheduling is performed by “Celery”: an open-source distributed task queue implemented in Python. Celery has been configured to use RabbitMQ as the message broker.

Most of the models are implemented as R scripts, but there are also some models written in Perl (Biodiverse).

Software that supports the R scripts have been installed on all the nodes in the cluster. Containers are currently not being used. The jobs usually only require one vCPU to run.

Users can run the jobs on common data sets or upload their own data. For example, the system has access to the Atlas of Living Australia (ALA) Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF), World Climate Data (1.5TB) and Australian Future Climate data (0.5TB).

Typically, jobs take between minutes to hours to run. However, some jobs can take days or months to run.

A.1.3. Future plans

BCCVL plans to make use of containerisation technology (using Singularity) to simplify the installation/distribution of software.

It is also investigating the use of Apache Mesos as a replacement for Celery.

A.2. Characterisation Virtual Laboratory Queensland (CVL@QLD)

A.2.1. Introduction

The Characterisation Virtual Laboratory (CVL) is an online environment for researchers to process and visualize data obtained from imaging instruments. Characterisation is a term that describes the use of imaging techniques in fields such as: neuroscience, structural biology, atom probe and X-ray science. Imaging data are generated by instruments such as: electron microscopes, light microscopes, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) scanners and X-ray crystallographers.

Characterisation involves processing large amounts of data. Imaging instruments produce data in the order of many terabytes per day, and that data sometimes needs to be processed in near real-time as the instrument is running. Therefore, the compute platform needs to be close (from a transfer or network perspective) to the instruments for quick and efficient data transfer. Also, any processing needs to be performed as part of a data management workflow, to ensure data from the instruments and the generated results are properly managed.

The CVL is a national project with deployments at different locations across the nation. This case study focuses on the CVL@QLD. At the time of the interviews, it was in beta deployment with a small set of users, so this case study focuses on their experience with implementation and initial usage, rather than with full production workloads. The initial set of instruments and users were mostly from The University of Queensland's Centre for Advanced Imaging (CAI) and Centre for Microscopy and Microanalysis (CMM).

For the researcher, CVL provides significant benefits over a single local computer connected to the instrument (a common setup prior to the availability of CVL):

- Access to more compute power. The researcher has access to HTC through a remote graphical desktop environment. They can access a CVL desktop through a Web browser client, or a native client installed on their local computer. The graphical environment is essential for running interactive visualisation programs.
- Access to pre-installed software. Software for processing the data is pre-installed in the environment, saving the researcher the trouble of installing and maintaining the software. They have access to both general imaging software as well as software specific to different fields of research.
- Access to the data captured from imaging instruments. Integration with a data management workflow to efficiently capture, manage and store the data coming off the instruments; and importantly to have the data readily available for processing by people on their team and their collaborators.

A.2.2. Current implementation

The CVL@QLD consists of a presentation node, where users connect to access their CVL desktops, and a HTC cluster where the CVL desktops run.

The presentation node is running on the QRIScloud Nectar node. It is a 4-core Nectar virtual machine.

The desktops run on compute nodes in the Awoonga HTC cluster—which is operated by QCIF [QCIF2019]. The cluster has dedicated 4 virtual machines to CVL@QLD, each with 20 vCPUs, 62 GB RAM and a GPU.

The Graphics Processing Unit (GPU) is mandatory for some software in the CVL desktop, and it significantly improves the performance of other software. Programs use the GPU for rendering and/or data processing. The compute nodes each have a single GPU.

Since the GPU hardware cannot be shared between virtual machines, it is a constraint on the service. Previously, the four physical compute nodes were each divided up into five virtual machines, each with 3-cores and 12 GB of RAM (supporting a total of 20 virtual machines in the cluster), but that meant only four users would have access to the GPU. Although that allowed for more simultaneous users, many wouldn't have a GPU. The current design guarantees each user has a GPU (as well as larger memory), but supports fewer simultaneous users.

The CVL@QLD implementation takes advantage of integration with QCIF's QRISdata collection storage service. The compute nodes have direct access to the data collections using IBM's General Parallel File System (GPFS) technology, which provides greater performance than protocols such as NFS. Also, CVL@QLD uses the existing access control mechanism from the QRISdata collection storage service, which allows data owners to manage who has access to the data. This enables data collections to be shared between members of the team and other collaborators. The use of existing services has made it easier to implement CVL@QLD: quicker and less costly than if it had to provide those services as a part of CVL@QLD.

The QRISdata collection storage service is connected to the UQ Research Computing Centre's Metropolitan Data Caching Infrastructure (MeDiCI): a high performance data storage fabric that is accessible across different campuses and, most importantly, where the imaging instruments are located. For transferring data into and out of the QRISdata collection storage service, users can use a wide variety of tools they are already familiar with: both specialised data management software like MyTardis and OMERO [OPME2019], as well as mounted to the researcher's local computer as a network drive (using NFS or SMB protocols).

Jobs to launch CVL desktops are scheduled onto Awoonga using a dedicated CVL queue. The queue is designed to schedule jobs to the dedicated nodes with GPUs, rather than to the general compute nodes in Awoonga which don't have GPUs. The user indicates how many hours they want their CVL desktop to run for when they launch it. They can choose up to 2 weeks. The Awoonga HTC cluster uses the PBS Professional® job scheduler.

Users can access their CVL Desktop via remote desktop software. It can be accessed via a Web browser, since the presentation node runs Strudel Web. Alternatively, users can install a native Strudel client program on their local computer. Command line access via SSH is also supported.

A.2.3. Future plans

At the time of the interview, CVL@QLD was in the process of integrating with the national CVL portal. This will improve the ability for CVL to manage users from an accounting point of view, and unify how users access CVL. Users will have a single entry point into CVL, and to be able to launch CVL desktops in any location supported by CVL. However, the location where users will choose to launch will usually be dictated by where their data is located.

The capacity of CVL@QLD needs to be increased. But this is limited by the compute capability that is available to it, since the full capacity of Awoonga's available GPU nodes is already being used. An interim plan is to incorporate university owned clusters into the available compute nodes: CVL desktops for users from that university will be offloaded to that university's cluster, freeing up general capacity for other users. This solution is not ideal, since it introduces complexity and does not fully address the capacity and limited number of GPUs for general users.

CVL@QLD is expecting a significant growth in the number of users it needs to support. For example, the CMM group is planning on using CVL@QLD as its preferred processing platform.

Licensing of commercial software is already being managed on a per-university basis. Although many software programs are pre-installed in CVL@QLD, access to commercial software depends on licensing. Users from universities with a license for that software may use it, via that university's license server, but users who do not have access to a licence cannot use it.

For users needing special software that is not already installed on the cluster, CVL@QLD is looking at a container-based solution. Users will be able to upload containerised copies of their software and for it to be managed using Singularity [SYLA2019].

CVL@QLD has some users who need large amounts of memory to run their jobs.

A.2.4. Challenges and opportunities for HTC

The main challenge for CVL@QLD is the availability of compute nodes—in particular, access to GPUs. For users that need to run programs that use a large memory footprint, the availability of RAM is another constraint.

The critical requirement of CVL@QLD is to have highly performant storage that is close to the computation infrastructure. It is geographically bound to locations near to imaging instruments, due to the large volumes of data they produce. This makes a general cloud solution impractical for its needs, since transferring the data would incur a significant bandwidth, latency and possibly financial cost. While data can be transferred over large distances, doing it both quickly and cheaply is difficult. Therefore, taking advantage of fast geographically-local connectivity is the cost effective approach.

Reliability is also a major consideration. When terabytes of data need to be stored and processed, lost or mishandled data is difficult to recover from.

The use of the Awoonga HTC demonstrates the use of HTC is suitable for CVL@QLD. Although the use of HTC for interactive desktops is not a traditional use of HTC, it can be accomplished to make more efficient usage of the available compute nodes.

For interactive use, a desirable feature for a HTC system is to be able to see how long a job has remaining. And also to be able to extend that time, if needed. Currently, the scheduling software in Awoonga does not allow for either of those functions.

A.2.5. Demand for HTC

CVL@QLD is currently using HTC and would use more of it, if it is available.

For a subset of CVL@QLD users, there is a demand for HTC with GPUs and/or high memory.

A.3. Characterisation Virtual Laboratory MASSIVE

A.3.1. Introduction

The CVL@MASSIVE is the primary deployment of the Characterisation Virtual Laboratory (CVL). It is located in Melbourne, and is designed to support national requirements that are able to be accommodated on the contributed hardware, and the requirements of, the MASSIVE partners (Monash University, CSIRO, Australian Nuclear Science and Technology Organisation (ANSTO) and University of Wollongong; and affiliate partners: ARC Centre of Excellence for Integrative Brain Function (CIBF) and ARC Centre of Excellence for Advanced Molecular Imaging (Imaging CoE)).

All CVL workloads are various types of image data processing that can be classified as high throughput computing. Typical examples include multi-subject neuroimaging studies and data parallel cryo-electron microscopy processing.

A.3.2. Current implementation

CVL@MASSIVE runs on MASSIVE, which is a high-performance data processing facility with over 5200 cores, 185 GPUs and 6PB of storage. CVL provides the interactive access to MASSIVE. Approximately 5% of MASSIVE has been dedicated for national CVL users (non-Partner) workloads, but often this is insufficient; MASSIVE partners are able to access the entire capacity. GPUs are a scarce resource that is in demand, even though CVL@MASSIVE has access to significantly more GPUs than CVL@QLD.

A.3.3. Future plans

It is expected that the demand for new HTC applications will grow. CVL@MASSIVE is introducing a new community of users (who were previously using laptops and desktop computers) to the capabilities of MASSIVE and HTC, and that is opening up opportunities for new applications.

A.4. Galaxy Australia

A.4.1. Introduction

Galaxy Australia is a Web-based platform for performing computation in biological research. It provides researchers access to over 850 tools, without needing a deep understanding of information technology. Workflow tools allow researchers to perform lengthy and complex processing.

Galaxy Australia is a part of an international community. It is one of the three “UseGalaxy” servers that are open to anyone to use, and provide a common core set of tools and reference genomes.

A.4.2. Current implementation

Galaxy Australia has three sites (Brisbane, Melbourne and Canberra), but users only interact with the service running in Queensland. They use a Web interface to upload data files, run jobs and retrieve results. The Queensland scheduler sends jobs to any of the three sites for execution according to the characteristics of the job (i.e. determined by the tool being run and the size of the data involved).

Each site consists of a head machine and a number of worker machines: 7 workers in Queensland, 6 workers in Melbourne, and 4 workers in Canberra. The Queensland site also has machines for the management database and to support file uploads. These machines are virtual machines from the Nectar Research Cloud. In total, approximately 277 vCPUs are used.

The scheduler communicates jobs to the other sites using Galaxy’s “Pulsar” protocol. At each site, the SLURM scheduler is used to manage the workers.

High memory and a large number of cores is required by some tools and jobs. Though there are also small and medium sized jobs too. Most of the workers in Queensland have 16 vCPUs and 64 GB RAM, as well as some of the workers in the other sites. The lowest worker has 4 vCPUs and 16 GB RAM.

The data for processing is packaged with the job, but the workers also have access to reference genome data sets. The reference data sets are mounted to each of the workers using the CernVM File System (CVMFS)—a file system developed by CERN for distributing and software and data.

A.4.3. Future plans

Galaxy Australia plans to add tools to support more communities. Currently, the tools are focussed on genomics. In the immediate future, proteomics and metabolomics will be supported. Front end interfaces customised for those particular areas of research may also be added.

Extra tools for genomics will also be added. For example, to better support the processing of single cell genomics, which requires large amounts of memory to process. The international community has over 5000 tools that can be included.

Some of the tools being considered will require GPUs and access to specialised hardware (FPGAs).

Data upload at the different sites is being considered as a new feature. This should reduce the need to transfer data between the sites, since data is currently being uploaded to the head site and then transferred to the site where it is processed.

Consideration is also being given to properly authenticate users and run jobs as those users. Currently, jobs are all being run under a single Galaxy user. Running jobs as individual users will allow better management and accounting.

Galaxy Australia is also trying to improve user experience, by using heuristics to estimate how long a job might take to run. For example, by providing an estimate based on the tool being used, the type of processing being performed and the size of the input data. This may help avoid users re-submitting jobs instead of waiting for the job to properly finish. This currently happens because they think the job is not running properly or has taken too long. This is usually an expectation problem with inexperienced users, who have not developed an understanding of HTC systems or the type of jobs they are running.

A.4.4. Demand for HTC

Dealing with sudden increases in demand is always a challenge. Sometimes Galaxy Australia is used for training sessions, which can suddenly increase the number of jobs it needs to process. While small jobs can be identified and sent to a separate cluster (Melbourne), there is a risk that these test jobs can impact the processing of real jobs.

A.5. ecocloud

A.5.1. Introduction

ecocloud provides an online computing environment for bioscience researchers. They can run R and Python scripts through RStudio and Jupyter Notebooks, access persistent storage for their data, find and use public datasets and run virtual desktops.

A.5.2. Current implementation

ecocloud currently runs on a pool of 24 Nectar virtual machines. Each virtual machine is an R3-Large flavour machine (with 4 vCPUs and 16 GB of memory) and can support 3-4 users. In total, approximately 116 vCPUs are being used. The pool of servers is managed by Jupiter Hub. The pool uses Docker containers and Kubunetes for deployment.

Users sessions are automatically terminated after a period of inactivity. Activity is determined by monitoring user interaction, network activity and running processes.

Users are able to install third-party Python and R packages. They have access to the Anaconda distribution of Python and R packages.

A.5.3. Future plans

ecocloud plans on adding a batch processing system similar to what BCCVL currently provides. Users will be able to create batch jobs to run a selection of scripts/programs. It is investigating the use of Apache Spark to implement this service. Their users have been asking for an easy to use batch system, to supplement the existing interactive services.

A.6. Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN)

A.6.1. Introduction

Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN) provides research infrastructure for ecosystem observations, by producing standardised and integrated measures of change in Australia's land-based ecosystem biodiversity. It also provides open access to data and research tools. TERN undertakes a number of different activities, but this case study only focuses on four activities which are especially relevant to HTC:

- Threatened Species Index (TSX)
- Remote sensing data processing
- OzFlux
- CoESRA Virtual Desktop

The Threatened Species Index (TSX) is a set of data products that measures changes in the relative abundance of Australia's threatened and near-threatened species. The index can be interrogated at a range of scales and for different groups of species. The index is updated once a year by processing a large amount of data from multiple sources.

The remote sensing data processing activity produces data products from satellite imagery. It currently uses Landsat data and is moving towards using imaging from Sentinel satellites from the European Space Agency (ESA).

OzFlux is a network of micrometeorological flux towers across Australia and New Zealand that measures the exchange of carbon dioxide, water vapour and energy between terrestrial ecosystems and the atmosphere. This exchange, known as "flux", is important for the understanding and prediction of ecosystem responses to disturbances such as: climate change, drought, precipitation, fire, land use and land management. TERN helps to collate, produce and publish the datasets from these towers.

The OzFlux activity produces data products for ecosystem science researchers. Data is collected from a network of approximately 30 micrometeorological Eddy Covariance flux stations across Australia and New Zealand.

The Collaborative Environment for Scholarly Research and Analysis (CoESRA) Virtual Desktop is a virtual desktop platform for research and analysis [TERN2019]. Users can remotely access a graphical desktop environment, which has a range of tools for processing environmental data (e.g. RStudio, Canopy, Kepler Scientific Workflow, KNIME, QGIS, Panoply and OpenRefine).

A.6.2. Current implementation

The Threatened Species Index is produced by processing large amounts of raw data. For bird species alone, over 60 data sources are combined. The data is confidential and is uploaded to volume storage for processing. The data needs to be processed in a consistent and repeatable way. Models for trend analysis are used to visualize the rates of change. The index is updated once a year, and therefore a significant amount of processing must be performed over a short period of time. For the current index on threatened bird species, over 60 data sources are combined together and processed using 25,000 jobs running on approximately 100 cores for 10 hours. That was done on Nectar QRIScloud cores, but it was approximately twice as fast on Tinaroo cores [UQRC2019].

Currently the OzFlux data products are generated by individual researchers who are the Principal Investigator of a tower. It is difficult to guarantee a reproducible environment, since each computer's setup may be different. It is also difficult to guarantee the availability of results, since their production depends on the availability of the researcher and their computer. Generating results can take up to several hours, or days, depending on which gap filling algorithms are used.

CoESRA virtual desktops uses a cluster of 30 vCPUs in the Nectar Research Cloud. Each virtual desktop runs on a virtual machine that has 2 to 8 vCPUs. Users have access to a home folder, shared data collections (in QCIF's QRISdata Collection Storage service) and pre-installed software.

A.6.3. Future plans

The Threatened Species Index will be expanded to cover other species, increasing the demand for HTC processing. Previously, only birds were included in the index. In 2019, mammals will be added. In future years, plants will also be added. This could double and triple its demand for HTC processing.

The remote sensing processing is a good candidate for processing on HTC, since it needs to run multiple independent tasks.

The OzFlux activity is a good candidate for processing on HTC, since it requires the consistent processing of flux data across all the towers using the same instance of processing software. The HTC would enable it to scale the processing, including gap filling, to generate reusable derived products from across all the towers in a single pipeline. Some of the machine learning neural network packages needs GPU processing to substantially improve the processing capability.

CoESRA aims to make all the TERN data accessible from its virtual desktops. Currently, users have to manually import the data they want to use. In the future, the platform will also be used to submit and execute HTC compute intensive tasks.

A.7. UQ RCC

A.7.1. Introduction

A large Genome Wide Association task was processed using Amazon AWS EC2, Huawei Cloud and the Nectar Research Cloud. The task consisted of approximately 500,000 jobs that ran over three days on approximately 900 CPUs. The major component of the task was using the MeDiCI caching architecture for distributing data to, and results from, the compute nodes. Commercial cloud charges amounted to approximately US\$26,000—comprising of both compute charges and data egress charges.

More details of this case study can be found in [ABRA2019].

Appendix B: References

- [ABRA2019] David Abramson, Jake Carroll, Chao Jin, Michael Mallon, Zane van Iperen, Hoang Nguyen, Allan McRae, Liang Ming, *A Cache-Based Data Movement Infrastructure for On-demand Scientific Cloud Computing*, Supercomputing Frontiers, SCFA 2019, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 11416, Springer, Cham, DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-18645-6_3](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-18645-6_3).
- [AROR2019] Ritu Arora, Carlos Redondo, Gerald Joshua, *Scalable Software Infrastructure for Integrating Supercomputing with Volunteer Computing and Cloud Computing*, Software Challenges to Exascale Computing, SCEC 2018, Communications in Computer and Information Science, vol 964, Springer, Singapore, DOI: [10.1007/978-981-13-7729-7_8](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-13-7729-7_8).
- [BHAT2017] Karan Bhatia, Google, *Google Compute Engine with HTCondor*, HTCondor Week 2017, https://research.cs.wisc.edu/htcondor/HTCondorWeek2017/presentations/ThuBhatia_GoogleCloud.pdf, visited 2019-08-07.
- [BERK2019] University of Berkeley, *BOINC*, <https://boinc.berkeley.edu>, visited 2019-10-11.
- [EGI2012] European Grid Infrastructure, *Glossary*, 1 June 2012, version 1, https://wiki.egi.eu/wiki/Glossary_V1#High_Throughput_Computing, visited 2019-07-01.
- [EGI2019] European Grid Infrastructure, *High-Throughput Compute Service*, <https://www.egi.eu/services/high-throughput-compute/> visited 2019-10-11.
- [OPME2019] The Open Microscopy Environment, *OMERO*, <https://www.openmicroscopy.org/omero>, visited 2019-10-02.
- [OSG2019] Open Science Grid, <https://opensciencegrid.org>, visited 2019-10-09.
- [QCIF2019] QCIF, *Awoonga User Guide*, <https://www.griscloud.org.au/support/griscloud-documentation/92-awoonga-user-guide>, visited 2010-10-11.
- [SING2019] Faith Singer-Villalobos, *For the Love of Science* (BOINC@TACC), <https://www.tacc.utexas.edu/-/for-the-love-of-science>, 24 June 2019, visited 2019-08-20.
- [SRIR2017] Rangarajan Srirangam, Rakesh Patil, *Azure GAHP Server for HTCondor*, MSDN, 12 September 2017, <https://techcommunity.microsoft.com/t5/AzureCAT/Azure-GAHP-Server-for-HTCondor/ba-p/306278> visited 2019-10-11.
- [SYLA2019] SysLabs, *Singularity*, <https://sylabs.io/singularity/>, visited 2019-08-07.
- [THAI2004] Douglas Thain, *Mapping Condor*, https://research.cs.wisc.edu/htcondor/CondorWeek2004/presentations/thain_mapping.pdf, visited 2019-08-07.
- [THAI2006] Douglas Thain, Todd Tannenbaum, and Miron Livny, *How to Measure a Large Open Source Distributed System*, Concurrency and Computation: Practice and Experience, volume 8, number 15, December 2006. <http://www.cse.nd.edu/~dthain/papers/measure-ccpe.pdf>, visited 2019-08-07.

- [TERN2019] TERN, *CoESRA Virtual Desktop*, <https://www.tern.org.au/TERN-CoESRA-Virtual-Desktop-pg29647.html>, visited 2019-07-16.
- [TSX2019] TERN, *Threatened Species Index*, <https://www.tern.org.au/Australia-s-new-Threatened-Species-Index-the-ASX-of-conservation-bgp4359.html>, visited 2019-07-16.
- [UQRC2019] Research Computing Centre, The University of Queensland, *Tinaroo cluster*, <https://rcc.uq.edu.au/tinaroo>, visited 2019-08-08.
- [UWM2019] University of Wisconsin-Madison, *HTCondor: High Throughput Computing*, <https://research.cs.wisc.edu/htcondor/>, visited 2019-08-19.